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Supramolecular solvent extraction of bioactives from coffee cherry pulp

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23 **Abstract**

24 The potential of supramolecular solvents (SUPRAS) is investigated for the extraction of bioactive
25 compounds from coffee cherry pulp, one of the major by-products generated in the coffee industry.
26 SUPRAS made up of hexagonal inverted aggregates of octanoic acid in ethanol:water mixtures provided
27 good extraction yields for bioactives (3.6 ± 0.3 mg caffeine g^{-1} and 0.9 ± 0.1 mg protocatechuic acid g^{-1}) at a
28 low solvent:sample ratio of 4:1 v/w and under mild operations conditions (5 min extraction at room
29 temperature). SUPRAS-based extraction was optimized and extracts were analyzed to identify the main
30 phenolic and alkaloid compounds. A variety of bioactives were present and extracts showed high
31 antioxidant capacity by different assays (45% for DPPH and 91% for ABTS). Extraction efficiencies with
32 SUPRAS were clearly superior than those obtained with organic solvents commonly used for valorization
33 of coffee residues.

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36 **Keywords:** supramolecular solvents; coffee cherry pulp; bioactive compounds; valorization

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47 **1. Introduction**

48
49 Coffee is the most popular beverage with a production of over 9 billion kg of beans per year and it is
50 cultivated in around 70 countries (International Coffee Organization, 2017). Coffee berries contain the
51 beans surrounded by different layers: first the silverskin, then the parchment, the mucilage, the pulp and
52 finally the skin (Esquivel and Jiménez, 2012). During the dry process, coffee cherries are sun-dried and
53 then they are dehusked to remove the skin, the pulp, the mucilage, the parchment and part of the
54 silverskin (Esquivel and Jiménez, 2012). These by-products are known as coffee husks. In the wet and
55 semi-wet processes, after separating ripened from unripe berries with water, fruits are de-pulped to
56 remove the skin and the pulp. The by-product or waste that is generated at this step is known as coffee
57 cherry pulp or coffee pulp (Murthy and Madhava Naidu, 2012; Pandey et al., 2000). In the wet process,
58 the beans are further fermented to remove the mucilage and the remaining pulp, then dehusked and finally
59 dried. After any of these three processes, the beans are roasted and generate as by-product the silverskin.
60 Considering that each 100 kg of mature fruits are composed by around 39 kg of pulp, 22 kg of mucilage
61 and 39 kg of parchment coffee, it is easily concluded that the amount of residues generated is extremely
62 high (Alves et al. 2017). Finally, spent-coffee grounds are generated during the production of instant
63 coffee and coffee brewing (Kovalcik et al. 2018).

64
65 In coffee producing countries, the unsafe disposal of the corresponding wastes has a negative impact on
66 the environment due to their high concentration in caffeine, polyphenols and tannins and high acidity
67 (Murthy and Naidu, 2012). The large-scale management of coffee waste is still challenging. A very
68 attractive strategy is its valorization to obtain benefits as compost, fuel, animal feed, bio-solvents or
69 bioactive compounds, among others. Bioactive compounds obtained from coffee by-products are mainly
70 alkaloids, melanoidins and polyphenolic compounds that exert beneficial antioxidant, anti-bacterial or
71 anti-fungal effects of interest for the food, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries (Belščak-Cvitanović

72 and Komes, 2017; Esquivel and Jiménez, 2012; Galanakis, 2015; Janissen and Huynh, 2018; Rodrigues et
73 al., 2017).

74
75 Extraction of bioactives from coffee by-products has been investigated using different solvents and
76 techniques. Moderate polar solvents are usually employed, such as methanol, ethanol or isopropanol,
77 sometimes mixed with water (up to 40% v/v) under typical sample to solvent ratios in the range 1:10-
78 1:100 v/w. Supercritical fluids (Andrade et al., 2012), subcritical water (Getachew and Chun, 2017), and
79 deep eutectic solvents (Yoo et al., 2018) have been also used. Techniques include conventional solid-
80 liquid extraction (Mussatto et al., 2011; Zuorro and Lavecchia, 2012), Soxhlet extraction (Murthy et al.,
81 2012), supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) with and without co-solvent (Andrade et al., 2012), ultrasound
82 (USAE) (Andrade et al., 2012; Getachew and Chun, 2017; Yoo et al., 2018) and microwave assisted
83 extraction (MAE) (Getachew and Chun, 2017; Pavlović et al., 2013). Spent coffee grounds have been the
84 most investigated coffee waste for the extraction of bioactives (Kovalcik et al., 2018) and in a lesser
85 extent coffee husks (Andrade et al., 2012) and coffee silverskin (Narita and Inouye, 2014). As mentioned
86 above, coffee cherry pulp is one of the main by-products of the wet processing of coffee (~40% of the
87 coffee is wet processed, Garde et al. 2017). However, it is still hardly investigated for the extraction of
88 bioactives despite its good antioxidant properties (Heeger et al., 2017, Murthy et al., 2012).

89
90 In this study, we investigate the suitability of supramolecular solvents (SUPRAS) for the extraction of
91 bioactives from coffee cherry pulp that was obtained by a wet process. SUPRAS are nanostructured
92 liquids produced spontaneously from colloidal suspensions of amphiphiles by self-assembly processes
93 (Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2018; Caballo et al., 2017). SUPRAS production involves the application of an
94 external stimuli (pH or temperature change, addition of salt or addition of a poor solvent for the
95 amphiphile) to the colloidal suspension where the amphiphiles arrange as three-dimensional aggregates,
96 which are usually normal or inverted micelles or vesicles (Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2010). The
97 application of an external stimulus diminishes the repulsion among the polar groups of the amphiphilic

98 molecules, which causes the growth of the aggregates that finally separate as a new liquid phase named
99 coacervate or SUPRAS (Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2018). The organized structures in the supramolecular
100 phase are held together by intermolecular interactions, such as ion-ion, ion-dipole, dipole-dipole,
101 hydrogen bonding, π - π and cation- π . Although these interactions are weaker than covalent bonds they
102 can produce very stable assemblies and provide multiple binding forces for extraction, which makes them
103 very efficient extractants (Caballo et al., 2017; Steed et al., 2007).

104
105 SUPRAS are tunable solvents since by changing the environmental conditions and/or the amphiphile
106 functional group/s is possible to tailor their composition and structure (Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2018).
107 Thus, SUPRAS have been designed to exclude proteins and carbohydrates from extraction by chemical
108 and physical mechanisms, respectively (Ballesteros-Gómez and Rubio, 2012). These versatile and
109 efficient extraction materials have proved successful for the recovery of a variety of compounds for
110 analytical purposes (e.g. PAHs, mycotoxins, perfluorinated compounds, drugs, dyes, etc.) (Ballesteros-
111 Gómez et al., 2010; Caballo et al., 2017). However, their application to the extraction of bioactives from
112 biomass or waste is still limited (Salatti-Dorado et al., 2019; Torres-Valenzuela et al., 2019).

113
114 Here, we investigate the suitability of SUPRAS produced by the addition of water to colloidal
115 suspensions of decanoic or octanoic acid in ethanol (Ruiz et al., 2007) for the extraction of bioactives
116 from coffee cherry pulp. SUPRAS components were selected from *Generally Recognized As Safe*
117 (GRAS) chemicals in order to produce a green and biocompatible solvent for further application in the
118 development of cosmetics, nutraceuticals or functional foods. SUPRAS extraction was optimized on the
119 basis of the extraction yields for caffeine and protocatechuic acid, the two most abundant bioactives in
120 this by-product (Heeger et al., 2017). SUPRAS extracts were further screened to elucidate the profile of
121 phenolic and alkaloid compounds and to measure their antioxidant activity.

122

123

124 Materials and methods

125 *2.1. Chemicals and solutions*

126 The list of chemicals and solutions is provided in the Supplementary Material (SI).

127

128 *2.2. Coffee cherry pulp*

129 Coffee cherry pulp was obtained using the wet method by the mechanical peeling of ripe coffee fruits
130 freshly harvested from an experimental lot located in Armenia City, Colombia (latitude 4°32'54'' north,
131 longitude 75°39'54'' west and altitude 1500 MAS). Coffee cheery pulp was dried to reduce water activity
132 and extend its shelf-life. The process was carried out at 60 °C during 8 hours, up to reach around 9.5% of
133 water content. Finally, sample size was reduced by using a coffee mill until obtaining a homogeneous
134 powder (particle size <2 mm).

135

136 *2.3. SUPRAS production and composition*

137 A variety of SUPRAS were produced by dissolving decanoic or octanoic acid in ethanol and then adding
138 water (pH ~3) to induce the growth of the aggregates of the amphiphiles. The volume of the ternary
139 mixture, consisting of variable percentages of ethanol and water and 5% v/v of amphiphile, was 50 mL.
140 The mixture was shaken on a vortex (Vortorex, Heathrow Scientific, Vernon Hills, IL, USA) for 1 min at
141 500 rpm and then centrifuged (Mixtasel BLT, Selecta, Cham, Suiza) for 5 min at 3,000 rpm. The
142 SUPRAS separated as a new liquid top phase in equilibrium with the bulk solution. Then both phases
143 (SUPRAS and equilibrium solution, EqS) were independently collected and stored in closed glass
144 containers at room temperature until use (~20-25 °C, within one week). Figure 1.1 shows a schematic for
145 SUPRAS production. The composition of each SUPRAS, which is dependent on the ethanol:water ratio
146 in the synthetic solution, was determined. The concentration of amphiphile, water and ethanol in the
147 SUPRAS was calculated as weight percent (w/w, %). Water content was determined by coloumetric Karl
148 Fischer titration (KF 831 model, Methrom, Herisau, Switzerland) after proper dilution with methanol. The

149 amphiphile content was determined by weighting SUPRAS aliquots (~200 μ L) before and after the
150 evaporation of water and ethanol. Finally, the ethanol content in the SUPRAS was calculated by weight
151 difference.

152

153 *2.4. SUPRAS extraction*

154 Figure 1.2 shows a schematic of the SUPRAS extraction procedure. Extractions were done in 2 mL-
155 microtubes Safe-Lock (Eppendorf Iberica, Madrid, Spain) by mixing 200 mg of coffee cherry pulp and
156 variable volumes of the different types of SUPRAS (and corresponding EqS) that were previously
157 produced as explained in section 2.3. The mixtures were vortex-shaken at 2,990 rpm for 5 minutes and
158 then centrifuged for 10 minutes at 10,000 rpm. A sequential design was used to determine significant
159 variables affecting the extraction yields of caffeine and protocatechuic acid, the two bioactives chosen as
160 models for valorization of coffee cherry pulp. Variables were optimized by varying each factor at a time
161 because of the different composition of the SUPRAS that were investigated, which can be considered as
162 different solvents. First, we investigated the effect of the amphiphile (decanoic acid or octanoic acid) and
163 of the ethanol concentration employed for SUPRAS formation. Conditions giving the maximum yield for
164 both target compounds were selected as optimal. Then we evaluated the effect of the ratios EqS:SUPRAS
165 v/v and sample:extraction solvent w/v. All the experiments were carried out at room temperature. For
166 each experiment, results were presented as mean \pm standard deviation for three individual extractions.
167 Statistical comparisons were performed with Minitab software Ver. 18 (Minitab Inc, State College,
168 Pennsylvania, USA) using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's tests (p-value < 0.05).

169

170 *2.5. Analysis of bioactive compounds by LC-MS/MS*

171 Caffeine, protocatechuic acid, 5-chlorogenic acid, gallic acid and caffeic acid were quantified by LC-
172 MS/MS in diluted SUPRAS extracts (dilution with methanol 1:5-1:100 v/v). Calibration curves were
173 prepared in methanol (0.1-20 mg L⁻¹). Other common bioactives found in the extracts were tentatively
174 identified based on characteristic transitions (Table S1) and semi-quantified against 5-chlorogenic acid

175 (due to the lack of authentic standards): rutin, 5-O-feruloylquinic acid, 3-O-coumaroylquinic acid, p-
176 coumaric acid, caffeic acid, n-O-dicaffeoyl quinic acids (three isomers), 4-chlorogenic acid, 3-
177 chlorogenic acid and 4-O-feruloylquinic acid. Quantification and target screening of bioactives was
178 carried out by LC-MS/MS (conditions specified in SI).

179

180 *2.6. Antioxidant activity assays*

181 SUPRAS extracts obtained under optimal conditions (200 mg of coffee peel, 670 μ L of SUPRAS and 130
182 μ L of EqS) were tested for the evaluation of the antioxidant activity by the DPPH and ABTS assays. The
183 inhibition percentage (or antioxidant capacity) was calculated (Régner et al., 2015). For the DPPH assay,
184 SUPRAS (blanks or extracts diluted 1:0 to 1:1000 v/v in methanol) were mixed with 250 μ L of DPPH
185 solution. The absorbance of the mixture was measured at 517 nm at 20 second-intervals during 20 min in
186 a multilabel plate reader Victor 3 1420 (Perkin Elmer, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). For the Trolox
187 equivalent (TE) antioxidant capacity assay, the ABTS^{•+} radical cation was produced as described in SI.
188 The assays were run by mixing 66 μ L of Trolox (0, 10, 30, 50 and 70 μ M diluted in methanol) or of
189 SUPRAS (blanks or extracts diluted 1:0 at 1:1000 v/v in methanol) with 154 μ L of ABTS^{•+} solution. The
190 absorbance of the mixture was measured at 732 nm at 40 second-intervals for 60 min and the percentage
191 of inhibition expressed as TEAC (Apak et al., 2013).

192

193 **2. Results and discussion**

194 *3.1. SUPRAS production and composition*

195 SUPRAS of different composition were prepared from ternary mixtures of octanoic or decanoic acid,
196 ethanol and water. Alkyl carboxylic acids have been previously reported to produce SUPRAS in hydro-
197 organic media (Ruiz et al., 2007), being tetrahydrofuran:water the mixture more used for analytical
198 purposes (Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2018). These amphiphiles give inverted micelles in water-miscible
199 organic solvents (e.g. THF, acetone, dioxane, propanol, butanol, acetonitrile, etc.) and the addition of

200 water (a “poor solvent” for the amphiphile) triggers the assembly of the aggregates into the SUPRAS, a
201 new highly packed phase with an inverted hexagonal arrangement (Figure 1.1). In this structure, the
202 carboxylic groups surround aqueous cavities while the hydrocarbon chains are dispersed in the organic
203 solvent. The SUPRAS is in equilibrium with a hydro-organic solution (EqS) containing the amphiphile at
204 the critical aggregation concentration. Both the SUPRAS and the EqS are immiscible. In this paper, a
205 mixture of ethanol:water was selected for the production of SUPRAS. Ethanol was selected against THF
206 because of its lower toxicity. Indeed, ethanol, decanoic and octanoic acid are authorized food ingredients.
207 These carboxylic acids were selected because they usually provide better extraction yields and they also
208 form SUPRAS in a wider range of conditions than acids with higher and lower hydrocarbon chain length
209 (Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2018).

210
211 Table 1 shows the composition of the SUPRAS that were produced by mixing octanoic or decanoic acid
212 (5% v/v) with variable volume ratios of ethanol and water. These ratios were determined by the minimal
213 and the maximal percentage of organic solvent required to form decanoic and octanoic acid-based
214 SUPRAS (Ruiz et al., 2007). The volume percentages of ethanol varied in the intervals 9.5-33 % and 19-
215 38% for octanoic and decanoic acid, respectively. As shown in Table 1, the concentration of amphiphile
216 in the SUPRAS was very high. So, SUPRAS contained a huge number of binding sites for bioactives.
217 This should enable the efficient extraction of the target compounds even at low SUPRAS/coffee pulp
218 ratios.

219
220 The concentration of water and ethanol in the SUPRAS increased as the percentage of ethanol did in the
221 synthetic solution (r-Pearson = 0.95-0.98 and 0.990-0.995, for water and ethanol with octanoic and
222 decanoic acid, respectively), while the concentration of amphiphile decreased accordingly (r-Pearson = -
223 0.95-(-0.98) and -0.986-(-0.995) with octanoic and decanoic acid, respectively). So, these SUPRAS can
224 be considered as environment-responsive (Ballesteros-Gómez and Rubio, 2012). Accordingly, SUPRAS
225 composition can be tailored by adequate selection of the composition of the synthetic solution (Table 1).

226 Likewise, as water is progressively incorporated into the SUPRAS, the size of the aqueous cavities of the
227 hexagonal aggregates increases and this behavior opens the door to the use of these SUPRAS as restricted
228 access liquids (Ballesteros-Gómez and Rubio, 2012). Thus, exclusion of polar macromolecules (e.g.
229 polysaccharides), takes place by size-exclusion mechanisms due to the small pores of the SUPRAS
230 network. On the other hand, proteins precipitate owing to the decrease of the dielectric constant and the
231 formation of macromolecular complexes with carboxylic acids. In this way, SUPRAS will extract
232 bioactives and simultaneously exclude major matrix components in coffee cherry pulp.

233

234 *3.2. SUPRAS-based extraction of bioactives from coffee pulp*

235 Optimization was carried out following the procedure specified in section 2.4 (see also Figure 1.2) and
236 considering the extraction efficiency obtained for caffeine and protocatechuic acid. These bioactives
237 were expected to be solubilized in the SUPRAS by mixed-mode mechanisms, namely dispersion
238 interactions with the hydrocarbon chains and hydrogen bonds with the carboxylic groups.

239

240 First, we investigated the influence of the composition of the eight synthesized SUPRAS (Table 1) on the
241 extraction yields of the target bioactives. For this purpose, both the SUPRAS and EqS, which are
242 immiscible, were added to the sample at a ratio of 1:1:2 sample:SUPRAS:EqS, g:mL:mL. The role of the
243 EqS was to favor the wetting and dispersibility of the sample. Figure 2 shows the results expressed as a
244 function of the percentage of ethanol used in the synthesis of the SUPRAS. Statistical operations
245 including ANOVA table and results of Tukey's tests are shown in Tables S2 and S3 of
246 Supplementary Information. The maximal extraction yields (i.e. around 1.6 mg/g caffeine and 0.39 mg/g
247 protocatechuic acid) were not significantly different for the octanoic and decanoic acid. However, the
248 optimal conditions were achieved at different synthetic conditions (at 33-38% and at 24% of ethanol for
249 decanoic and octanoic acid, respectively).

250

251 Regarding the composition of these optimal SUPRAS, the decanoic acid-based SUPRAS had a higher
252 ethanol (25.6-32.7%) and water (14.4-19%) contents compared to the octanoic acid-based SUPRAS (i.e.
253 21% of ethanol and 12.3% of water) (see Table 1). This different behavior can be qualitatively interpreted
254 as follows: the two binding forces driving the extraction of the target bioactives (hydrogen bonding and
255 dispersion) decrease and increase, respectively, with increasing length of the hydrocarbon chain (Burke,
256 1984). Short-chain carboxylic acids are better proton donors than longer carboxylic acids. So, considering
257 the high polarity of the target bioactives ($\log K_{ow}$ -0.07 for caffeine and 0.86 for protocatechuic acid,
258 source: DrugBank) and the number of hydrogen bonds acceptors (3 for caffeine and 4 for protocatechuic
259 acid), it is reasonable to assume that extraction will be favored with SUPRAS made up of octanoic acid,
260 because stronger hydrogen bonds can be established. In the case of SUPRAS synthesized from decanoic
261 acid, more water and ethanol were necessary, particularly for caffeine, to increase hydrogen bonding. In
262 fact, recoveries for the target bioactives were highly correlated with SUPRAS water content (r-Pearson
263 0.96 and 0.97 for caffeine and protocatechuic acid, respectively for decanoic acid-based SUPRAS).
264 Overall, maximum extraction of bioactives at the lowest consumption of ethanol (cost-benefit ratio taking
265 into account that similar prices are expected for food grade natural octanoic and decanoic acids), was
266 found with SUPRAS made up from 5% v/v of octanoic acid, 24% v/v of ethanol and 71 % v/v of water.
267 These conditions were selected as optimal for further studies.

268
269 Secondly, we optimized the influence of the ratio SUPRAS:EqS. For this aim, extractions were carried
270 out with a total volume of 1.2 mL of SUPRAS+EqS and the content of the SUPRAS phase varied from 33
271 to 100%. Results are shown in Figure 3 and the corresponding statistical operations including
272 ANOVA table and results of Tukey's tests are shown in Tables S4 and S5. The results clearly show
273 that extraction yields increased as the SUPRAS phase did, especially for caffeine, a highly polar
274 compound that partitioned between the SUPRAS and the EqS. Lower losses of protocatechuic acid were
275 observed in the EqS due to its lower polarity. Maximum extraction efficiencies for both bioactives were

276 reached for extractant phases containing 83% and 100% of SUPRAS, so these phases were selected for
277 further studies.

278
279 Next, we studied the sample:extractant phase ratios (mg:mL) in the range 1:3 to 1:6. For this purpose, the
280 amount of sample was kept constant (i.e. 200 mg) and the volume of the extractant phase varied from 0.6
281 to 1.2 mL. As can be seen in Figure 4 (see also Tables S6 and S7 for Tukey tests), not significant
282 differences were found in the extraction efficiencies for both bioactives in the whole interval for
283 SUPRAS:EqS and in the interval 1:4.5-1:6 for SUPRAS. Since absolute values were slightly higher for
284 SUPRAS:EqS in the interval 1:4-1:6, a ratio 1:4 was selected as optimal. Significantly higher solvent to
285 sample ratios have been reported for the extraction of bioactives from solid coffee waste, many times
286 using pretreatment, high temperature or energy-assisted techniques. For example standard solvent
287 extraction procedures based on aqueous methanol or ethanol have been reported at ratios of 30-40 mL/g
288 and carried out at room temperature or 50 °C (Mussato et al., 2011; Zuorro and Lavechia, 2011). Lower
289 ratios (9-10 mL/g) were reported by Murthy et al. (2012) with Soxhlet extraction using aqueous
290 isopropanol at 50 °C and pretreatment with viscozyme and by Pavlović et al. (2013) by microwave-
291 assisted extraction. The use of deep eutectic solvents also required high ratios of 17-100 mL/g under
292 ultrasonic assisted extraction at room temperature or at 80 °C (Mouratoglou et al, 2016; Yoo and Lee,
293 2018).

294
295 Extraction yields of 3.6 ± 0.3 mg caffeine g^{-1} and 0.9 ± 0.1 mg protocatechuic acid g^{-1} were obtained under
296 optimal conditions, which are specified in Figure 1. These values were in agreement with those
297 previously reported by Heeger et al. (2017). The content of caffeine and protocatechuic acid in coffee
298 cherry pulp obtained by wet or semi-dry processes from six varieties varied from 3.4 to 6.8 mg g^{-1} and
299 from ~ 0.2 to 3.1 mg g^{-1} , respectively.

300

301 3.3. *Comparison of the extraction efficiency of SUPRAS and conventional organic solvents for bioactives*
302 *in coffee pulp*

303
304 The extraction efficiency of SUPRAS for caffeine and protocatechuic acid was compared with that
305 obtained by organic solvents commonly used for extraction of bioactives from coffee residues (e.g.
306 methanol, ethanol, acetone, and acetonitrile). Aqueous mixtures with polar solvents are also commonly
307 employed for this aim.. However, since these mixtures limit the extraction of less polar bioactives (e.g.
308 flavonoids), we preferred to do a comparison with pure polar solvents for wide scope extraction purposes.
309 We employed the same extraction procedure for polar solvents than that optimized for SUPRAS (i.e.
310 solvent:sample ratio of 4:1 v/w and experimental conditions as reported in Figure 1.2). SUPRAS
311 extracted ~7-fold more caffeine ($3.6 \pm 0.3 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$) than methanol ($0.31 \pm 0.05 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$). Values for ethanol
312 ($0.187 \pm 0.004 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$), acetone ($0.205 \pm 0.009 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$) and acetonitrile ($0.22 \pm 0.02 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$) were even
313 lower. Results for protocatechuic acid were also better for SUPRAS that extracted this bioactive ~11-fold
314 more efficiently ($0.9 \pm 0.1 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$) than methanol ($0.12 \pm 0.07 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$). Ethanol ($0.055 \pm 0.009 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$),
315 acetone ($0.041 \pm 0.006 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$) and acetonitrile ($0.0272 \pm 0.0007 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$) were even less efficient. Results
316 for other phenolic compounds identified in the following section are shown in Figure S1. The multiple
317 binding sites and adequate balance of hydrogen bonds and dispersion interactions provided by SUPRAS
318 could be the reason for this higher extraction efficiency.

319
320 3.4. *Phenolic compounds and alkaloids profile in SUPRAS extracts*

321 SUPRAS extracts obtained under optimal conditions were analyzed by LC-MS/MS to investigate their
322 content in phenolic compounds and alkaloids. The most abundant phenolic compounds were
323 protocatechuic acid ($0.9 \pm 0.1 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$), gallic acid ($0.25 \pm 0.02 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$) and 5-chlorogenic acid (0.13 ± 0.01
324 mg g^{-1}). Other phenolic compounds were present at significantly lower levels: rutin ($30.5 \pm 2 \text{ } \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), 5-O-
325 feruloylquinic acid ($17.3 \pm 0.5 \text{ } \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), 3-O-coumaroylquinic acid ($13.4 \pm 0.4 \text{ } \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), p-coumaric acid
326 ($4.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ } \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), caffeic acid ($2 \pm 0.2 \text{ } \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), n-O-dicaffeoyl quinic acids ($1.6 \pm 0.1 \text{ } \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, sum of three

327 isomers), 4-chlorogenic acid ($1.1 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), 3-chlorogenic acid ($0.34 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) and 3-O-
328 feruloylquinic acid ($0.4 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$). The isomeric form of each class of compound was assigned on the
329 basis of relative retention times and main fragments according to (Angelino et al., 2018). Figure 5 (LC-
330 MS/MS chromatogram) shows the most abundant phenolic compounds in SUPRAS extracts. Regarding
331 alkaloids, caffeine ($3.6 \pm 0.3 \text{mg g}^{-1}$) was the major compound followed by trigonelline which was detected
332 with about 15-fold lower abundance.

333
334 Samples were also extracted with conventional solvents (i.e. methanol, ethanol, acetone and acetonitrile)
335 under the same experimental conditions that those used for SUPRAS and the extracts analyzed by LC-
336 MS/MS to quantify the most abundant phenolic compounds (protocatechuic acid, gallic acid, 5-CGA and
337 rutin). Figure S1 shows the results obtained, which prove the higher efficiency of SUPRAS compared to
338 the most used organic solvents.

339 Levels of 5-chlorogenic acid in *Castillo* variety were lower than those reported from other varieties
340 cultivated in South America (*Caturra*, *Catuai*, *Maragogype* from Honduras and *Bourbon* from El
341 Salvador, $0.7\text{-}0.9 \text{mg g}^{-1}$, Heeger et al., 2017). The same study reported gallic acid and rutin at levels
342 below $100 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ in these varieties. A higher value of 0.73mg g^{-1} of gallic acid was reported for a
343 *Bourbon* variety cultivated in Congo.

344

345 *3.5 Antioxidant activity of SUPRAS extracts*

346 Phenolic compounds are the main contributors to the antioxidant activity of coffee and by-products
347 (Belščak-Cvitanović et al., 2017). The antioxidant activity of SUPRAS blanks was negligible under any
348 dilution or experimental condition. The antioxidant activity of SUPRAS extracts was measured by the
349 DPPH and ABTS assays. For this purpose diluted SUPRAS with concentrations in the ranges $0.14\text{-}36 \text{g L}^{-1}$
350 1 and $0.3\text{-}287 \text{g L}^{-1}$ for DPPH and ABTS assays, respectively, were tested. Linearity for antioxidant
351 activity versus SUPRAS concentration was observed up to $15 \text{g SUPRAS L}^{-1}$ and $25 \text{g SUPRAS L}^{-1}$ in the

352 DPPH and ABTS assays, respectively. At these concentrations, the DPPH and ABTS antioxidant capacity
353 were $45\pm 1\%$ and $91\pm 4\%$. The Trolox equivalent (TE) antioxidant capacity at $25\text{ g SUPRAS L}^{-1}$ was 334
354 μM .

355
356 The DPPH antioxidant capacity of coffee pulp extracts obtained under different extraction conditions,
357 (which are hardly comparable) has been previously reported (Murthy and Naidu, 2012; Silva et al., 2013).
358 Thus, DPPH activity of 65% has been found for extracts (0.5 g L^{-1}) obtained by Soxhlet extraction of 100
359 g sample with isopropanol:water 60:40 v/v at a solvent to sample ratio 10:1 v/w followed by evaporation
360 to dryness (total yield 18.1%) (Murthy and Naidu, 2012). A similar DPPH antioxidant capacity (65.3%)
361 was measured in coffee pulp extracts (20 g L^{-1}) obtained by extracting the samples by three consecutive
362 times with ethanol (sample:solvent ratio 1:10 w/v) and evaporating the extracts to dryness (Silva et al.,
363 2013). On the other hand, the values here obtained by the ABTS assay (corresponding to $40\text{ }\mu\text{mol TE g}^{-1}$
364 coffee pulp) were in accordance with those reported reported by Heeger et al. (2017) in the range 51-64.9
365 $\mu\text{mol TE g}^{-1}$ coffee pulp (in weight, ~10% humidity) with different varieties of coffee cultivated in South
366 America.

367
368 **4. Conclusions**
369 SUPRAS provides an efficient alternative extraction approach for the isolation of bioactive compounds
370 from coffee cherry pulp, a less investigated coffee by-product than coffee husks, coffee silverskin or spent
371 coffee grounds, but of major importance in the wet processing of coffee. SUPRAS extracts, rich in
372 caffeine and polyphenols, can be of interest for the development of nutraceuticals, functional food or
373 cosmetics. The extraction approach is simple (it is carried out at room temperature and atmospheric
374 pressure in a single step and without external energy, such as ultrasound- or microwave-assisted
375 extraction). While drying and grinding are common industrial steps, vortexing and centrifugation can be
376 replaced by a more gentle mixing approach during longer extraction times (to keep the extraction
377 efficiency rate) followed by decantation and filtration. Further purification steps for

378 concentration/separation of bioactives and for recovery and reuse of SUPRAS components are also
379 probably required for industrial applicability. For this aim, different strategies could be employed, such as
380 evaporation and/or freeze-drying for water and ethanol removal, back-extraction of bioactives with a poor
381 solvent for the amphiphile (aqueous polar solvent mixture), dry fractionation for removal of octanoic acid
382 and lipids or anionic exchange resins to retain octanoate after changing the pH to ~7. Nevertheless, the
383 presence of octanoic acid in the final commercialized products should not be problematic since it is a food
384 authorized ingredient and also can benefit the stability of bioactives For further implementation at
385 industrial scale, the benefits of the amphiphile-rich extracts for enhancing the stability and bio-availability
386 of bioactives will be addressed in the future.

387

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393

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Figure captions

Figure 1. Schematic picture of the SUPRAS production and the extraction of coffee cherry pulp.

Figure 2. Extraction yields of caffeine and protocatechuic acid as mean \pm standard deviation ($n=3$). Significant differences are indicated by different letters on the top of the bars (Tukey tests). Extraction of coffee cherry pulp (200 mg) with SUPRAS (400 μ L) and corresponding EqS (800 μ L) produced by mixing decanoic or octanoic acid in ethanol:water mixtures according to the conditions specified in Table 1. Percentages of ethanol on the X-axis represent the concentrations of this solvent in the synthetic solution.

Figure 3. Extraction yields of caffeine and protocatechuic acid as mean \pm standard deviation ($n=3$). Significant differences are indicated by different letters on the top of the bars (Tukey tests). Extraction of coffee cherry pulp (200 mg) using an extractant phase consisting in SUPRAS + EqS. The content of the SUPRAS phase varied from 33 to 100% and the volume of the extractant phase was 1.2 mL. The ratio solvent to sample was 6:1 v/w. SUPRAS synthesis conditions: octanoic acid 5% v/v, ethanol 24 % v/v and water 71% v/v.

Figure 4. Extraction yields of caffeine and protocatechuic acid as mean \pm standard deviation ($n=3$). Significant differences are indicated by different letters on the top of the bars (Tukey tests). Extraction of

528 coffee cherry pulp (200 mg) with SUPRAS or SUPRAS:EqS 88:17 v/v and different solvent to sample
529 ratios 3:1-6:1 v/w. SUPRAS synthesis conditions: octanoic acid 5% v/v, ethanol 24 % v/v and water 71%
530 v/v.

531
532 **Figure 5.** LC-(ESI-)MS/MS extracted ion chromatograms for the most abundant phenolic compounds in
533 optimal SUPRAS extracts. Abbreviations: 5-CQA (5-O-Caffeoylquinic acid); 3-CouQA (3-O-
534 Coumaroylquinic acid); 5-FQA (5-O-Feruloylquinic acid); n-DQA (n-O-Dicaffeoylquinic acids).

Figure 1

Fig.1

Figure 2-4

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 5

Table 1

Chemical composition of SUPRAS obtained from different ternary mixtures of amphiphile:ethanol:water (% , v/v). The optimal SUPRAS is shown in bold.

	Chemical composition of the synthetic solution (%, v/v)			SUPRAS		
	Amphiphile	Ethanol	Water	Chemical composition (% , v/v)		
				Amphiphile	Ethanol	Water
Octanoic acid	5	9.5	85.5	89 ± 1	5 ± 1	5.5 ± 0.3
	5	19	76	76 ± 1	14.7 ± 0.2	9.7 ± 0.4
	5	24	71	67 ± 1	21 ± 1	12.3 ± 0.3
	5	33	62	45 ± 2	32 ± 2	23.2 ± 0.4
Decanoic acid	5	19	76	83 ± 1	11 ± 1	6.05 ± 0.07
	5	24	71	75.7 ± 0.2	16.1 ± 0.1	8.1 ± 0.1
	5	33	62	59.9 ± 0.5	25.6 ± 0.5	14.4 ± 0.2
	5	38	57	48.2 ± 0.6	32.7 ± 0.7	19 ± 1

Laura Sofía Torres-Valenzuela: Investigation, Resources, Writing - Original Draft. **Ana Ballesteros-Gómez:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. **Soledad Rubio:** Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.